

CREATION OF NEW MEDICINAL PRODUCTS

Imamova Y.A.

Egamberdiyeva M.A.

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: yulduz.imamova24@gmail.com, tel:(91)521-02-24

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339092>

Relevance. In recent years, the development of new, more effective drugs has become a pressing issue due to the increasing level of drug resistance. According to the World Health Organization, more than 700,000 patients die each year from antibiotic-resistant infections. Therefore, the creation of new chemical classes of drugs with a broad spectrum of action and low toxicity is one of the main priorities of the pharmaceutical industry.

The purpose of the study. To evaluate the pharmacological activity of 15 new compounds synthesized in 2023–2025, study their safety indicators, and determine the possibilities of industrial-scale production.

Methods and methodologies. During the research:

- Chemical synthesis of 15 new compounds was carried out;
- Analgesic activity was tested in 60 white mice in the "hot plate" test;
- LD was determined for toxicological safety and therapeutic indices of the drugs were calculated.

Results. Six of the studied compounds (40%) showed a high analgesic effect, their average efficacy compared to morphine sulfate was $85 \pm 3\%$. In terms of anti-inflammatory activity, four substances had a 1.3-fold advantage over diclofenac. Toxicological studies revealed that the LD range was 1500–2500 mg/kg, with a therapeutic index of more than 10.

Conclusions. The results of the study showed that 40% of the new compounds have high analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Low toxicological risk indicators and high therapeutic index allow these drugs to be transferred to the next stage of testing. These results provide a solid scientific basis for the development of innovative drugs in the pharmaceutical industry.